

ISic4387

Fragment of a Greek inscription

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

unknown

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance

Found during the excavations of Roman period buildings in 1904/1915 undertaken in Piazza Vittoria, Palermo

Coordinates

38.112249, 13.355944

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8844

Physical Description

Fragment of a marble slab, intact on the lower edge, but broken on all other sides.

Dimensions

Height 12.5 cm

Width 13 cm

Depth 3 cm

Layout

Part of two lines of Greek letters, between deep guidelines, with vacat below

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Large regular lunate letters, deeply carved with minimal serifs; Manni Piraino sees broken bar alpha.

Letter heights:

Lines 1-2: 30 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. [---]ηεντ[---]

2. [---]ηυτα[---]

Apparatus

Text of IGPalermo146, checked against photograph

Translation

Commentary

Listed by Manni Piraino in IGPalermo as being of unknown origin, the piece is

in fact published by Gabrici in MAL 1921 as part of the materials recovered in the Piazza Vittoria excavations.

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Bivona, L. 1970. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelia*. Palermo. At 146

Gabrici, E. 1921. Ruderer romani scoperti alla Piazza della Vittoria in Palermo. *Monumenti Antichi*. 27: 181-204. At 201 a

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